

Developing Corporate Services in an Agile Environment

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ABSTRACT

DoD represents an environment of continuously changing mission requirements that requires our Information Systems to adapt to accomplish new tasks, quicker, in a more efficient manner. Agility is the only way we will be able to keep up with this change. But there are subtleties that must be considered as we adopt various agile methods: secure, protect, control and authenticate are all elements needed to posture our Information Technology systems to counteract the real and perceived threats in today's environment. Many systems have been tasked to ingest process and analyze different data sets than they were originally designed for and they have to interact with multiple new systems that were unaccounted for at design time. Leveraging the tenets of security, we have devised a new framework that takes agility into a new realm where the product will be built to work in a service-based environment but is developed using agile processes. Even though these two criteria promise to hone the development effort, they actually contradict each other in philosophy where Services require stable interfaces, while Agile focuses on being flexible and tolerate changes up to much later stages of development. This framework is focused on enabling a successful product development that capitalizes on both philosophies.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

"Assurance is the level of confidence that software functions as intended and is free of vulnerabilities, either intentionally or unintentionally designed or inserted as part of the software" -- DOD

Stakeholder needs and goals drive the agile development methodology. This tends to focus the developers on the capability being developed rather than the environment in which it needs to execute. Attempting to retrofit an application into a "secure" environment once it is "developed" is the infinite flaw when developers take this approach. Even though many want to exclude secure applications from being developed using agile methodologies, this study contends that with some light-weight rigor up front, security does not have to be a deterrent to leveraging agility. In fact, in today's environment of wiki leaks, hacking, virus attacks, etc security must be considered above all else when developing new and innovative applications because if the capability cannot be run in a secure environment most companies and most definitely DoD will not even consider its use. Security must be built in, not bolted on; therefore, it must be integrated throughout the Agile process.

In order to capitalize on agile development methods and re-useable corporate services, we need to state some objectives for our framework. Initially we need a solution that is generally applicable to all systems, non-virtualized and virtualized. Time and effort must be predictable otherwise we could lose sight of our end goal by continuing to develop without any perceived deadline or endpoint. We want to streamline the Certification & Accreditation (C&A) process to be able to provision capabilities that use C&A'd compliant services to enable shorter delivery times. Outline the

attributes of these conforming services, so that other applications will be able to develop to the "rules" and ultimately expedite development, certification, accreditation, and deployment processes. Finally, defining a framework that includes a native governance mechanism will enable the corporation to bound its Enterprise, recognize the gaps in technology and authority to allow for a prioritization of resources to focus on the most important mission needs.[2][3]

2.0 SECURITY FRAMEWORK

Security tends to be integrated and managed at the later stages of development so the resulting framework needs to prioritize security at the same level of functionality to ensure the development of a complete system. The assumption here is that if we conquer security in an operational system at inception without performance degradation, we've hit on all aspects of the development.

A typical development starts with a hardware platform with minimal security components so that software can be developed freely without any encumbrances. As a developer we optimize in this "free" environment that allows us the "break" typical security rules (just to prove the concept). But once we are ready to integrate and test to our key performance parameters we must now integrate our capability in an operationally relevant environment; which means we need those security features that allow us to deploy. If we were not building in the expected security environment all along then we've got quite a mess to contend with, because if we were claiming success in our "unencumbered" environment we very well might have to re-engineer the development to meet the security and performance requirements. The bottom-line is if our application cannot run in a secure environment then we failed.

The security conditions and therefore requirements typically are fluid because they are designed to counter unpredictable internal and external threats. These are the reasons why we want to use agile methods along with corporate services: to decrease this deployment time and to be able to provision new capabilities in a manner that meets or even exceeds our mission needs. But security is a big mountain to climb and we can rarely get a "head nod" on certification and accreditation requirements just to meet a deadline. However, if we can somehow harness predecessor services that have been previously through a rigorous C&A and leverage its certified and accredited state, metrics show[1] that the C&A process can be significantly streamlined to enable an early delivery. By leveraging previously tested and validated components and services, the developers can rapidly garner solid results. By reusing these assets, we will be able to develop or integrate applications more rapidly, with better quality while reducing costs. It is important to also objectively measure in terms of resource development hours what we have saved by using what we already have. This can be achieved by using tools that provide quantitative and qualitative metrics to measure reuse level and to calculate the ROI for the enterprise services and components portfolio.

3.0 AN AGILE SECURITY POSTURE

3.1 Defining Agile

Being agile is not only a state of being, but a mind-set that bridges customers' expectations to developers' techniques. The definition

of agile is “responsive” and “swift”, which in today’s ever changing environment to quickly respond to change is the difference between being successful and failing, it is that drastic. There are a variety of agile approaches and methodologies, but they all center on the stakeholder and continually are in refinement mode. Generally, agile software development teams respond to the volatility of building software through an incremental, iterative work tempo. Some teams using Scrum call these Sprints others call them Spins or Iterations. The DoD is moving away from waterfall development primarily because of the unpredictable threat environment and the need to deliver capability in months not years.

One of the keys to agile software development is the ability to refine or refactor code throughout the development of a capability. The fundamental thought is to make concise manageable modifications to your code to improve the design, making it easier to understand and to change. Refactoring enables you to evolve your code slowly over time, to take an iterative and incremental approach to developing your application. Which is why delivering smaller chunks of working code is more palatable to the stakeholder and it feeds the continuous feedback loop that enables developers to refine their product. Communication is never perfect and correction through feedback loop is essential.

3.2 How to Determine if your team is Agile

Many development teams believe they are agile, many shout it from the mountain tops they are agile, but if the team does not conform to certain tenets of agility, then they cannot claim the title. Scott Ambler of Ambysoft conducted a survey of 293 respondents based on the following criteria: Value: Validation: Stakeholders: Self-organization: Improvement: [6]

Agile methods are quite different in emphasis from traditional linear-type development methods. The most obvious difference is that they are less document-oriented, usually emphasizing a less documentation for a project. They actually are more design or code-focused leveraging the source code as a key element of the documentation.

Agile methods are adaptive rather than predictive.[7] Traditional methods tend to try to map out the software development process at a detailed level over years, this works well until things change. So their nature is to resist change. The agile methods, however, welcome change. They try to be processes that adapt and thrive on change. Agile development allows the developer many chances to reevaluate the direction of a project throughout the development lifecycle. As mentioned earlier, depending on the tempo at which the team is developing will determine how often operational code is delivered. Typically, Sprints are every 30 days and Spins tend to be on a 90 day cycle. The approach is “just in time” development in order to get in the cycle of “build a little, test a little, deploy a little”. This allows the developers to “refactor” the code, as stakeholder requirements become better understood throughout the process. Some interesting results of the survey show that producing working software, meeting daily and continuous/active improvement of processes is really the essence of agility.

The following delineates the process for agile software development in basic terms that is repeatable and extensible:

1. Brainstorm with your stakeholders to understand the goals for the software
2. Build the best possible software solutions to meet expectations, even the ones that are not known at the beginning of the project
3. Create an initial “proof of concept” share with stakeholders
4. Evolve and adjust the prototype through multiple iterations in a series of milestones – based on feedback rapid results and frequent releases of work-in-progress is required to ensure the project’s real needs are on track.
5. Refactor the code and architecture throughout the entire lifecycle of the project to improve and streamline the internal structure
6. Include the stakeholder as part of the development team through short brainstorming sessions – along with using and testing the evolving prototype – without taking up too much of time
7. Deliver a final core software product that meets stakeholder expectations, within schedule and budget (keeping in line with the theme of under-promise over deliver).

3.3 CORPORATE SERVICES

When we talk about services, most people think SOA; which has lost its flair as being perceived as idealistic. However services are the basis of how we will be able adapt in this environment of shrinking budgets, emergent threats, growing volumes of data and an infrastructure that must evolve to keep up. Services enable reuse and it provides a common approach to performing certain tasks that can be used by multiple applications. Some Agencies are even using the services paradigm as a means to resource their infrastructure (Infrastructure as a Service)! Services enable us to provide a standard way to provide a function or purpose that can be reused and leveraged indefinitely based on an agreed-upon Service Level Agreement (SLA). Some important reasons for creating a corporate service environment are to achieve the following:

- Optimized resource utilization, which lowers capital expenditures
- Greater flexibility through dynamic resource allocation
- Simple, cost-effective upgrades
- Reduced operations workload
- Support for on-demand usage models
- Removes resource management and security responsibilities from application code
- Enables reuse of existing infrastructure services

Providing corporate services will enable rapid, agile development of services and orchestration of processes for deployment into a Service-based architecture. Corporate services include infrastructure components such as registries and design-time governance as well as the frameworks within which services are developed. Developers can use existing services for distributed, real-time, event-driven, multi-platform applications by taking

existing infrastructure services enables rapid deployment models, resulting in greater agility of IT. In order for network and security infrastructure to be incorporated into the Service-Based Architecture, it is necessary for those components to provide corporate services that can be integrated using services-focused methodologies. These include standards-based interfaces to supported capabilities. These support agility through dynamic configuration and modification of the metadata based policies that govern the delivery and security of services within the Services-based Architecture.

Also a standards-based platform through which shared network and security is available is essential. Services can be implemented and deployed, encouraging reuse and enforcement of organizational standards upon service implementations.[9]

3.4 PERVASIVE SECURITY SERVICES

Through focusing on agile provisioning services, we want to reduce the overhead and ultimately the complexity of deploying a secure service to the Enterprise. The attempt is to have all new applications be able to assign all of their security relevant behavior to other services of the enterprise. A Services-based architecture could be leveraged to allow for the development and provisioning of services that rely on “security-services” for all their security needs. The following sections describe the types of security services that have been implemented successfully. They shape a paradigm that allows for unique service development without the need to duplicate the security aspects within the application, rather, leverage the security services available. Figure 2 shows this relationship. There are a number of security considerations specific to service-based environments. The security model adopted for these environments should incorporate users, Web services and general enterprise services, which in themselves are fully distributed and fault-tolerant. It is essential that the final security model is based on existing standards and tools and should support identity authentication at both the user (i.e., human or non-person entities) and enterprise services levels. The following are the constraints that should be followed:

- The model has to support ownership and control of sensitive data and tracking of access by the data steward
- In this heavily distributed computing environment we need to restrict the scope of interactions between clients and the corporate IT infrastructure. In other words, thin client is the primary approach to alleviating the client-server bottleneck paradigm.
- Providing different security roles on a per-user and per-service basis ensures customization of client interactions. In other words, the stakeholder only pays for what they need in terms of performance and resources.
- Data Isolation has to be achieved using logical isolation methods, since the physical storage and processing are shared
- Strong security is needed for identity and access control, as well as for stronger encryption and key management
- Use of Open Sources enables sharing and leveraging resources, but may open up information to be viewed by other users

Platforms within a cloud-enabled, service-based architecture should be designed to operate in a distributed fashion for maximum performance and scalability. The following delineates different configurations:

- Commodity machines and floating processes make for flexible resources, however they complicate security and require new capabilities to protect data at rest/transit/processing and to cleanse memory and processors after use
- Parallel Processing expedites speed of processing but requires new generation of software that are optimized for parallelism

and are capable of protecting information during search and processing

- Search capability can be easily expanded to cover all data hosted on the clouds, however with multi-user clouds, there is a stronger need for encryption and key management to protect information from cloud users that are not authorized members of a specific community

Finally, security capabilities cannot negate the benefits that the Services-based environment enables and they are as follows:

- Cost and performance can be distributed over the organizations utilizing the security services
- Elastic capabilities to spur new processes over the available ubiquitous computing resources
- Ease of entry by simply subscribing to the cloud service, you are covered by the security

Figure 2 Security Framework for Agile Development [12]

3.4.1 Authentication Service: Authentication is a process that verifies a user's identity to ensure that the person requesting access is in fact, that person to whom entry is authorized. This is a service that sanctions a security assertion that associates the identity of a person and an authenticator. The AS validates the rule in the security strategy before initiating the authentication process and subsequently provides access. Access however, is valid for a limited period of time after which the authentication process will be required again.

3.4.2 Rules Service: This is a security service that confirms a security assertion on a rule, individual or device to ensure the conventions are being followed. One of the primary functions of this service is to interpret the rules for the applications invoking the service. As each assertion is processed, an audit log is maintained to monitor each event and adjudication of each event to ensure a policy-driven approach to each decision is followed. This audit log will enable continuous monitoring of the rules controlling the domain and would provide forensics if an intrusion or security breach occurs.

3.4.3 Link Service: This is a security service that validates and establishes communication links between other services and applications. After it is invoked, it leverages the authentication service and the rule service to validate the attributes of the link requestor and the link recipient. There also is an audit log of the connection that is maintained to include link time frame, information type transmitted and person-to-person (P2P) or computer-to-computer (C2C) identifiers.

3.4.5 Governing Services: This security service primary focus is to maintain a common baseline of applications and report on the

version and other metadata that defines version availability and compatibility. It also audits the authenticity of the baseline applications and maintains an audit log of how well the applications meet the current Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and finally this service provides overall health and status information on all aspects of the application including the services that are invoked as a result of an application being employed.

3.4.6 Verification Service: This security service provides protection mechanisms to prevent information flow to an unintended recipient based on security attributes, authentication and access control. This service is responsible for verifying data tags and the classification labels and ensuring encryption keys are appropriately utilized for information flowing between applications as well as continuity and information integrity of service between connections.

3.5 Agile Development of an Interoperable Enterprise [10]

The agile development focuses on developing a product quickly and in a flexible manner to enable change when the need arises. It also is designed to allow adoption of new requirements as part of the process to allow systems to be delivered in an incremental manner to meet the most critical requirements first. Theoretically, these dynamic characteristics make the Agile approach to building systems somewhat unstable to be utilized in a System of Systems (SoS) environment or as part of an enterprise services unless strict adherence to external interface standards and performance criteria is enforced. The baseline for an Information Sharing Environment should be founded on the following assumptions:

- Common standards should be agreed upon by all stakeholders prior to development or implementing changes. These standards not be developed in a vacuum and then enforced; but continuously updated throughout all phases of the lifecycle.
- The functional standards implementation approach should leverage existing standards to enable information sharing and adoption of Commercial of the Shelf components.
- Structured and unstructured information sharing standards apply to data, documentation, related business processes, and respective production methods.
- The initial architecture should not specifically preclude sharing of specific information types that is currently outside the mission scope (i.e., DoD mission, terrorism information, emergency response, healthcare, environment, etc.).
- Metadata should:
 - Ensure that information is understandable, searchable, and accessible based on common characteristics across the enterprise.
 - Metadata tags should provide accuracy and relevancy indicators of the information and should be securely bonded to the information.
- Common methods of Access Control for Information Sharing are essential to collaboration.
- User training should be provided as a continuous process to support a successful operations and implementation of standards.

3.5 Deploying Automated Secure Systems

The development of systems, even in an agile environments, need to keep the operational aspect of the system capable of adapting to new threats through a flexible configuration capability. The goal should always be to develop standardized configuration processes and standardize interfaces to achieve a dynamic and automated net-centric data strategy objective which will harden and defend our networks. The closed loop approach should start with deploying a flexible system with initial security capability to automatically adapt to the threat environment while providing services to all stakeholders.

The logical defensive method of protecting systems includes providing timely and accurate configuration control of networks through the use of an enterprise-wide set of capabilities to measurably improve systems security posture. It is recommended that these methods utilize sensors that enable an automate creation, publication, assessments and reporting of asset configuration and compliance data. This approach will reduce operator burden by enabling Machine-to-Machine data sharing to reduce duplicate entry and prioritize persistent and wider attacks over isolated attacks on less sensitive environment.

The development and adoption of global data standards allow enterprise tools to share data with local systems and develop comprehensive defenses that allow the whole enterprise to achieve a higher security level. The process of standardization might require retrofitting existing tools with standardized interfaces and ensure future tool procurements include the standards. In a SoS environment we need to listen to the Network Operators and Defenders, and make requirements management transparent and collaborative effort to ensure that the added new capabilities take into consideration the required security criteria. Additionally we need to provide users at all tiers with accurate and timely situational awareness to allow intelligent choices by stakeholders.

We need to limit point-to-point and custom interfaces and utilize the common Services and Messaging Bus as the main method of interfacing between different parties. This will enable the Publish and Subscribe architecture and limit the number of duplicate messages on the transport resources. Additionally, it allows all services to continue developing their services to meet future demands and assume that the available input streams will be delivered on time.

3.5.1 Detect

One of the most important operational needs is to have a system that performs the required tasks and provides the level of security to the stakeholders that it is under positive control of a trusted entity that is protecting their well being and property in the best way possible. This level of assurance can only be accomplished by providing a continuous monitoring capability to discover hostile actions and detect errors and attacks as soon as possible. This mechanism should be tied to automated reporting tools to inform of the error and its characteristics. The second part is providing an audit management tool to inspect logs of actions and access and determine via thresholds or historical records the possibility and identity of a hostile actions. Analysis is part of both capabilities as well as a method on its own to analyze trends and steer the developers and maintainers to better prioritize actions.

3.5.2 React

The first action network administrators do upon discovering security violations is to close security holes and isolate infected areas. This is most effective when we have reliable detection tools and have interoperable methods of sharing discoveries with other users. Common languages and interfaces make this action essential. The next step is to deliver a fix to stop further infection from taking place and close any back doors and disable the source of the violation. Since this is a critical action that requires critical time, we need to fix important issues first, and then move to sanitize the infected area to re-activate all services. In a service-based environment, if the culprit violation resides in an enterprise service, taking that service down without directly affecting applications and other services is the optimum situation.

3.5.3 Upgrade and Update

It is a common practice to have a subscription to one of the leading malware detection and removal tools to receive the most recent patches and methods. However, we need agile methods to apply the patches to all elements of the enterprise and ensure that there are no

updates. Another important factor is ensuring data on the move and data at the halt are always protected by utilizing the appropriate Data Encryption methods. Several algorithms are readily available, but implementing a system that enforces the utilization of such techniques requires a standard methodology. When building systems, agile or standard processes, we need to make sure that this becomes a priority.

The latest trend is to have a tailored and dynamic Access Control service that adapts to the threat level and enables users to access the authorized information. Now this approach should enable the native agile methods to excel in delivering such a dynamic product. This approach needs to be fueled by a Dynamic Attribute Management algorithm where access decisions can be based on all the latest information in order to let them adapt the response to each request based on environmental and personal attributes provided by the interactive environment.

3.5.4 Predict and Invest

Technology trends play an important role in security area especially following the general hacker and known competitor and Adversary Trends. Agility is the best approach when building and provisioning systems that depend on high security to ensure protection of information and resources. It is also essential to monitor industry trends to understand the next wave of products and their affect on the enterprise security postures. The use of data standards and service based architectures to facilitate on-demand data sharing can help in detecting malware and sharing information with trusted entities to ensure better awareness of risks.

3.5.5 Alternative Planning

It is understood that once a system is connected to the common Internet or has multiple users on the enterprise, internal and external attacks will happen by intentional or unintentional actions of the users. This leads us to ensure that we have processes and development and maintenance approaches to recover data and systems once they have been attacked and alternative resources to ensure continued operations of the enterprise when the system is attacked and being recovered.

3.5.6 Meeting the Next Generation Capability needs

The discussion thus far has mentioned development systems and capabilities to deliver services to the stakeholders in today's environment. However, the DoD and many leading commercial and governmental agencies are quickly developing and implementing plans to migrate to the a cloud based environment where services and/or data storage will be handled by third parties within or outside the enterprise. This approach necessitates the development of agile method to deal with threats and attacks quickly and re-instantiate reliable services to all stakeholders in an expedited manner. The loss of service or attacks will now affect the whole enterprise or possibly many dependent and attached enterprises that utilize the cloud or its services. Agility in defending the services, data, and identities is essential if this implementation method is to succeed. Figure 3 depicts the phases we in the DoD will continue to need to evolve through to reap the benefits of agile development methodologies. Phase 1 shows the AS-IS deployment to a single stovepipe system and even though agility can improve delivering capability quicker, it is only to one system. Phase 2 shows a interoperable connected set of systems for which agility can improve capability delivery to even more systems, but it still is not pervasive. Phase 3 shows even more improvement with a common backbone in a service center environment and then Phase 4 shows the pervasive implementation of cloud with infrastructure as a service, software as a service, etc which gives the best Return on Investment (ROI) when it comes to agile development.

Figure 3 Agility for the DoD Next Generation IT Strategy

4.0 THE SECURITY FRAMEWORK for Agile Developers

The security framework that we constructed was based on guidelines out of NIST Special Publication 800-53 Revision 3 on Information Security [8]. We are leveraging the “families” of security elements that are related to the Technical class as well as one Operational class in that we believe that these elements drive software development and provisioning. A security framework must ensure policy definition, enforcement, measurement, monitoring, and reporting is evident for each capability development. However, because defining and implementing policies alone cannot ensure security, the framework must also: 1) cover confidentiality, integrity, and availability, and 2) address how those elements map to a secure component. In this paper, we establish a high-level framework that you can use either as a starting point for a new security program or as a blueprint for assessing your current security program. We present a new information security framework that resolves the problems of the existing models. We demonstrate the need for security elements such as availability, utility, integrity, legitimacy and confidentiality. This new framework is used to address aspects of security at a fundamental level. Our approach leverages the agile development methodology to build services that have a high degree of reusability for our applications so that unique security components do not have to be repeatedly built in to each of the applications. The Service Imperative basically defines the type of service required for that class of security family. For the Access Control security family, the service imperatives are as follows:

- Institute an authorization service to authenticate user attributes and data classification.
- Ensure all data is tagged appropriately to enable sharing at the same classification or higher level.
- Institute an integrity checking mechanisms to ensure applications, data or users cannot access information they are not authorized or accredited to access.
- Ensure appropriate blocking mechanisms are in place to counter rogue applications or users.

For the Audit and Accountability security family, the service imperatives are as follows:

- Institute an automated audit logging capability to capture all access, authentication, assertions and denial events.
- Institute an automated audit logging capability to capture all access, authentication, assertions and denial events.
- Ensure audit reports are generated at a pre-defined tempo and that they include metadata such as time stamps, identification data, adjudication information and out of bounds data.
- Institute an archival capability to save dated reports to enable forensic analysis to occur in the event of a security breach.

- Collect metrics on all security events to load balance security services.

For the Identification and Authentication security family, the service imperatives are as follows:

- Create a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) to make available to all applications to enable single sign-on, ensure privacy, provide authentication, maintain integrity and guarantee non-repudiation.
- Provide the ability to enable reciprocity for authentication between systems outside the domain.
- Provide the ability to uniquely identify individuals, devices and applications to uphold integrity.

For the System and Information Integrity security family, the service imperatives are as follows:

- Leverage the authentication service to ensure the right data is available to the right applications.
- Ensure all data is tagged appropriately to enable sharing at the same classification or higher level.
- Institute an integrity checking mechanisms to ensure applications, data or users cannot access information they are not authorized or accredited to access.
- Institute an integrity checking mechanisms to ensure applications, data or users cannot access information they are not authorized or accredited to access.
- Institute data checking mechanisms to ensure the veracity of the data as it is used by different applications.
- Log all metadata on data requests and transmission to capture data provenance to further ensure data integrity.

For the System Communication and Protection security family, the service imperatives are as follows:

- All security services must be bounded and self contained to maximize reusability and to avoid ambiguity with other non-security services.
- Create a robust health and status monitoring service in order to detect and counter threats such as: [11]
 1. **Malicious Code:** This is transmitted to the victim's site through Attachments, Piggybacking, Internet Worms, Web Browser Exploits, Hacking, and Affiliate Marketing.
 2. **Theft of Data:** This is done through hacking, identity theft, access manipulation, and other methods.
 3. **Infiltration:** This includes social and technical infiltration of the information systems and the personnel managing these important assets. The adversary agents get access through physical or logical access holes in the security and steal, destroy and manipulate information.
 4. **Man-In-The Middle:** This type of attack involves intercepting data while in process or in transmission between source and destination. The attacker either steals, destroy or changes the data to harm the competitor.
 5. **Data Source/Results Corruption:** This type of attack is accomplished by attacking the information via malware or physical destruction of the system hosting the information.
 6. **Denial of Service (DOS):** This type of attack usually consists of the concerted efforts of a person or persons to prevent the information source services from functioning efficiently or at all, by temporarily or indefinitely flooding the servers with requests beyond their ability to respond.
 7. **Unauthorized Access:** This is the process by which an outsider gains access to a system or network, or an authorized person gains access at a higher level than he/she legitimately needs in order to take an unfair advantage of the system to destroy, damage, or transmit the information to an unauthorized user or for an unaccepted use.
 8. **Distributed Denial of Service:** This is where many computers have been taken over illegally by the offender and directed to overwhelm the intended victim.

9. **Domain Name Server (DNS) Attack:** This type of attack is where the attacker accesses and manipulates the DNS to block access to the host.

10. **Vulnerability Exploitations:** In this type of attack, an adversary uses a vulnerability that is a known attribute of the system to provide an unauthorized means to access and/or modify the contents or to terminate its functionality.

- Monitor and log metrics to capture out of bounds data, communication links, data volume transmission and length of connection in order to load balance, guarantee availability, protect privacy and maintain the integrity of the system.
- Institute checking mechanisms to validate all data that is transmitted is tagged with appropriate classification labels.
- Ensure any remote user, application or device is authenticated prior to access.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a framework to address how to incorporate corporate security services leveraging agile methodologies. To deliver capabilities using a “just in time” development model, adjustments must be made throughout the hierarchy of the team responsible, from developer to stakeholder. Security is the catalyst in determining if a capability truly meets mission needs. If security is not designed or “baked-in” the development then security will be added as an afterthought ultimately not meeting mission needs and making the application more vulnerable. If we are going to deliver these capabilities in a timely fashion we must have an agile service-based framework to realize success. This is what we have provided in this paper. This framework has been used successfully in the Federal Government. As technologies change and methodologies adapt, this framework will morph along with all other aspects of development in order to stay relevant and supportive of successful secure application deployments. The longer-term vision is to have adaptive development where automated situational awareness is made a priority at the system inception. We must prioritize approaches that enable the implementation of distribute security policy and remediation guidance within the agile framework. Finally, we should encourage the Improvement of system workflows, and enforce the utilize industry and DoD data standards as the basis for new developments within an agile process.

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